

A STUDY ON CATEGORIES OF DEPRESSED CLASSES PEOPLES WITH SPECIAL REFERNCE TO VELLORE DISTRICT

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ABSTRACTE

The Depressed Classes gained statutory recognition for the first time when the Government of India Act 1919 provided for the political representation of the Depressed Classes through nomination, on a number of public bodies. Classes included only the Untouchables not the tribal and uncivilized folk.. The Untouchables of India have been known by legion of terms at different times or by different terms by different people. The British administrators termed these people as Depressed Classes. They coined this term because of their depressed social and economic status of Vellore District. But it was opposed by the members of the North Arcot District Adi-Dravida Mahajanasabba. They said, that the Adi-Dravidas are not Hindus, and therefore the term Adi-Hindus should not be used in the place of Adi-Dravida, In 1921 Census the Paraiyas, Panchamas, Pallas, Vettiyan etc. were listed as Adi-Dravidas, and as a consequence the figures for Adi-Dravidas showed a marked increase. Among the Depressed classes also there were sections spreading into Tamil, Telugu and Kannada languages also.

Introduction

The Depressed Classes Mission Society of India said, that the term Depressed Classes included only the Untouchables not the tribal and uncivilized folk. He said, that eventhough they are civilized by a strange sociological action, they had been reverted at the outer gate of civilization from which they could neither proceed away nor recede in the South Borough Committee arrived in India on 27th January, 1919 the leaders of the Out Castes presented their representation stating that they have been dehumanised by socio-religious disabilities almost to the

status of slaves and they had been denied citizenship. They wanted the Committee for restricting the Depressed Classes to cover only the Untouchables. Dr.B.R.Ambedkar in his memorandum categorically pointed out that the Untouchables and the Depressed Classes

The term Depressed Classes gained statutory recognition for the first time when the Government of India Act 1919 provided for the political representation of the Depressed Classes through nomination, on a number of public bodies. Their numerical strength became a must for their representation in the political bodies. Thiru J.T.Martin Census Commissioner began to prepare an estimation in 1921. It is little bit confused over the exact or specific definition of the Depressed Classees, yet he prepared a rough estimate of the minimum number which could be considered to form Depressed Classes of the Hindu Community. Moving a resolution for the enhancement of educational facilities for the children of Depressed Classes on 23 February 1928, M.R.Jayakar observed By the term Depressed Classes, mean those who suffer from social disabilities such as the Untouchability. In the CenBUB Report of 1921 it was stated that over six million people covering nine castes listed as Depressed Classes, They are (1) Adi-Drauidas, (2) Cha.kkiliyan, (3) Holey, (4) Cheruman, (5) Madiga, (6) Mala (7) Pallan (8) Paroiyan and (9) Bensman in the Madras Presidency. But in 1931 Census, the definite norm was fixed to identify the Depressed Classes. They were identified on the basis of Untouchability and exactly enumerated. Accordingly their population was 15.5% of the Madras Presidency.

Vellore is one of the important towns in the northern Tamil Nadu and it was the capital city of erstwhile North Arcot District. Right from the early times, it played a vital role in the Socio-Economic and Political history of Tamil Nadu in various aspects. Vellore district is an area of about 6,077 kms. It is an inland lying between 12.21° and 13.56° of the northern latitude and 80.10° of the eastern longitude. The district is bound on north by the Andhra Pradesh, on the south by Thiruvannamalai district and on the west by Karnataka State. Kancheepuram is one

of the ancient cities of India, which is on its eastern boundary. Vellore is the head quarters of the district.

Untouchables

The Untouchables of India have been known by legion of terms at different times or by different terms by different people. Therefore, the description of this people have been remained as a matter of controversy. In Puranas they were called, Asprusyas, Avarnas, Chandolas, Suanpachas, Antiyajas, Jambavans, Vanishals, Antyawasi, Antya, Bluuigi etc., Dr. B.R.Ambedkar says, that the Untouchables were the broken men of the Aryan society and hence called them. In order to express this condition they are called Depressed Class People. And further the terms suppressed oppressed and sub-merged were used as substitutes for the word Depressed. To indicate them as the lowest caste in the Hindu society, they were called as Pariahs, Panchamas, Out caste-caste, Out castes Hindus, Adi-Sudras, Exterior Castes, Excluded Castes, Protestant · Hindus or Non-Caste Hindus, Adi-Dravidas, Scheduled Castes, Harijans, Dalits etc.

It is generally applied to a persons in the dipressed classes of Hindus society. This term first appeared in print in 1909. The word Untouchability is a literal translation of the Hindi word Achut. The Webster Dictionary describes as a member of a large hereditary group in India having traditional Hindu belief and quality of defiling by contact the person, food drink of a member of a high caste and formerly being strictly segregated and restricted to menial works. The terms Untouchability and Untouchables have been hated, as they amount to a degrading appellation for the people concerned. The term reminds the fallen state of the people by a constant sting, says B.S.Murthy in his book Depressed and Oppressed. Dr.B.R.Ambedkar used this term in the titles of various books to highlight the degrading position of the people and arousesympathies for their political rights. JhC Untouchables were Hindus but they were not in the · Hindu Society! And they were segregated from the Hindu society. Therefore, the appellation Out Castes Outcaste-Hindus, Excluded Castes, Neglected sectiona of Hindu Society and Exterior Castes were coined to the definite relations of the Untouchables with the Caste - Hindus.

The Untouchables are called Out Castes because they are outside the caste-system and therefore, they are not the members of the Hindu Society. They are also called Avarnas which means not included in the Chaturvarna System. However, the word Untouchables has now disappeared from ordinary parlance following wide spread education Caste - Hindu realisation by the caste Hindus and the Constitutional provisions. Since the thesis is concerned with the Depressed Classes living conditions particularly deals about them in Vellore District, the terms currently in force to indicate their nomenclatures may be defined.

The Depressed Classes

The expression Depressed Classes is made up of two words Depressed and Classes. Depressed means pressed down and Classes means the plural form of the peoples group. Thus, in the ordinary parlance the term Depressed Classes should mean a group of people pressed down. This term began to be used in official records in the last decade of the 19th century, as a result of the Government's resolution to extend educational facilities to the lowest rung of the society. At the time the expression Depressed Classes was deemed to include Untouchables, Aborigines, hill tribes, Criminals and the like classes. But, with the advent of Europeans, the problem of the Untouchables acquired new dimensions different from those of the tribal people. Untouchability was taken as the scale and the tribals who are not Untouchables were oriented. So the non-tribals alone were taken as Depressed Classes. The Depressed Classes was in current during the Round Table Conferences. Dr.B.R.Ambedkar, Rao Bhadur Rattaimalai Srinivasan and the other delegates of the Conferences fluently and frequently used this term during the deliberations of the Conferences. The term was changed into Scheduled Caste after 1935.

Scheduled Castes

The Round Table Conference to discuss the future political concessions by the British in India held at London in 1931, Ambedkar demanded a Separate Electorate for the Untouchables and also made a special demand for a Change of nomenclature. He proposed that the Untouchables could be called as Protestant Hindus or Non-Conformist Hindus¹² What emerged instead, when the electoral

award was made and eventually incorporated into the Government of India Act of 1935, was the new official term Scheduled Castes. The Government of India in 1935 listed all the hereditary Untouchable Communities in the different provinces in a Special Schedule. An order-in Council issued under the Government of India Act in 1935 designated of the castes in the list as Scheduled Castes?. In the Madras Presidency, eighty six Untouchable brands came under the category of Scheduled Castes.

The scheduled Castes became the legal administrative term of the British Government since 1935. In the case of providing them political representation, educational and employment reservations, the terms

Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes were used and the were incorporated in the Indian Constitution in articles 366(24) and 366(25) respectively. In the Census enumeration also these terms were recorded. The population of Madras Presidency in 1941 was 4,98,40,564 and out of this 81,52,226 belonged to Scheduled Castes. It is to be noted that in 1941 the population was enumerated on the basis of religion such as Hindus, Muslims, Christians, Sikhs, Jama, Parsi, Buddhists and Jews. And the Scheduled Castes was not included into the Hindu groups but they were enumerated as a separate entity as Scheduled Castes.

Article 331 of the Indian Constitution empowers the President of India to notify the castes as Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. He has the power to include or exclude any castes from these lists. Article 335 of the Constitution makes provision for the reservation of services and posts to Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. Uniouchability has been taken as the scale to prepare such list of Scheduled Castes. After the publication of the list of Scheduled Castes many castes which were not found in the list volunteered themselves to be included in the list because they wanted to enjoy the political privileges guaranteed in the Constitution for the Scheduled Castes. Say for example» The Andhra Gonda MalwJana Sangh.am, Guntur District wanted Gonda to be included in the list of the Scheduled Castes 14 The Jatavas of United Provinces also wanted to be included in the Scheduled Castes list.

A few castes protested against their newly conferred Scheduled Castes status. Say for example: · The Khaiks of U.P. Considered it a blot and Disgrace on the fair name of their caste and earnestly described and desired exclusion of the caste from the Scheduled Castes as soon as possible. In 1942, so also, the Nadars of Ta.mil Nadu considered it a blot and disgrace on the fair name of their caste and earnestly desired exclusion of the caste from Scheduled Castes. Further the Nadars were included in the list of Backward Classes. whether they are Hindus or converted to Christianity. Hence, the term Scheduled Castes is appropriate only in legal and Governmental matters, otherwise for social and political purposes it is of little use Article 366(24) of the Indian Constitution defines the meaning of Scheduled Castes and Article 341 of the Constitution empowers the President of India to notify names of the Scheduled Castes.

Harijan

Harijan is the name introduced by Mahatma Gandhi. In Hindi Children of God. In the Hindu temples there were, the Devadasis, the girls who took part in worshipping ceremony and also served the priests. Sometimes they gave birth to children who were called Harijans. That is why we dont like the Name?. Mahatma Gandhi really wanted to remove the inferiority and give sense of superiority. But people did not take it in that way. Accordingly to Gandhiji, Harijans means children of God Hari! The first to use this word Harijan was Narashima Metha a great saint who belonged to Nagar Brahmana Community. He used it praise of God Vishnu and so Gadhiji used the same for Untouchables as a better mean of identifying them in the society

The Congress Government recognised the, term Harijan and issued an order in 1947, stating that the Government have directed that the term Hariian, Should be used to denote persons belonging to the Scheduled Castes in all public records except in proceedings of statutory enactments, until the statute is amended¹⁹ But the term Harijans is not found in the Constitution anywhere in the form of Amendment. In 1938, B.R.Ambedkars group in the Bombay Legislature Council protested against the use of the term Harijans, for statutory purpose at the

time of consideration of a Bill aiming at the amendment of the Local Boards Act. P.G.Solanki, Ambedkars Lieutenant told the house not to give recognition to the term.

Dalits

The word Dalit is the Sanskrit form of the broken or split from ascender. Again the Depressed Classes or Scheduled Castes were called as the Dalits, This was used by Dr.Ambedkar to mean the members of the Mahar Community in Maharashtra but later it was used to mean generally all the Scheduled Castes, and the Neo-Buddhists, landless labourers and those who were economically exploited The word Dalit in Marathi means poor and down trodden. It denotes the Untouchables who are not included in the Chaturvarna system of Hindu Society²⁶. On 26th January, 1950 we have abolished Untouchability as meant for deterrent punishment. Hence, according to Constitution there is no Untouchables. We have seen above some of the nomenclatures of the Depressed Classes as the common names on the Nationwide basis. Let us examine certain nomenclatures of the Depressed Classes and their concept in the Vellore District.

Adi-Dravidas

The term Adi-Dravidas is commonly used to denote the Untouchables of Tamilnadu but it was not used in record prior to 1920. The change in the nomenclature of the Untouchables into Adi-Dravidas was taken place as a result of the prolonged struggle of the leaders of Adi-Dravida Mahajana Sabha and by the keen efforts taken by Rao Bahadur M.C.Rajah, a leader of the said Sabha. In 1857 the Adi-Dravida Mahajana Sabha was started by some leaders of the Community with the aim of uplifting the Community and it was registered in 1892 under the Madras Society Registration Act of 1860. Some of the leading personalities who took keen interest and played the vital role were P.V.Subramaniam Pillai, a leading merchant of P.V.Venkatachallum condiment, Mylai Chinnathambi Pillai (Father of M.C.Rajah), Pandit C.Ayyothi Doss, a famous Buddhist Revivalist in Vellore District. Rao Bahadur M.C.Rajah, Rao Bhadur Rettaimalai Srinivasan, the liberator of the Adi-Dravidas, R.Verraiyan, a champion of the Depressed Classes liberation movement of

Kongu Country, M.Madurai Pillai the Mayor of Rangoon, J .Sivashanmugam Pillai, the former speaker of Madras Legislature Assembly and the first Master Degree holder of the Adi-Dravida Community and a galaxy of other elders.

In 1917, M.C.Rajah led a deputation consisting of Messers P.V.Subramaniam Pillai, K.Munusami Pillai, V.Rajaratnam Pillai, Venugopal Pillai, Tiruppugazh Ammal had presented a memorial to E.S.Montagu and Lord Chelmsford praying for a change in the name of the Depressed Classes. The relevant portion of the memorial reads. The very name by which these people are referred to breaches contempt. We should therefore, request the Government to help us in our efforts to attain social elevation by issuing orders that hereafter in all Government communications, we should be designated as Adi-Dravidas or the Original Dravidas, this bringing us into line the non-Brahmin Hindus who spoken of as Dravidas

Ayyothi Doss started a Tamil Journal called Tamizhan and he emphasized in the journal that original Tamizhan are the Adi-Dravidas or Adi-Tamizhan as the sons of the soil. He also submitted a detailed memorandum to the Commissioner of Census Report to enlist the term Adi-Tamizhan instead of Pariyar in the Census Report. A.Perumal Pillai a renowned Tamil Scholar of Tiruchirapalli has written a research book History of Adi-Dravidas and defined the detailed account of the term Adi-Dravidas. They have also published journals like Diravida Mitran (1885), Diravida Pandiyan. (1885) Adi-Draoida (1919), Adi.-Dravida Mitram (1939) etc., In 1920. Dr.G.A.Natesan tabled a motion in the Madras Corporation to change the name Panchama into Adi-Draoidas and a mass meeting of Adi-Drevidas was also held to support his resolution. From 1920 onwards the term Adi-Dravidas came to exist in the records of the Corporation of Madras. M.C.Rajah was instructed by the Adi-Dravida Mahajana Sabha to move the resolution in the Madras Legislative Council for the change of the nomenclature of the Depressed Classes. Accordingly. M.C.Rajah, while moving the resolution in the Madras Legislative Council for the change of the nomenclature of the Depressed Classes, made a forceful speech advancing valid arguments in support of his resolution. Rajah

examined the real connotation of the terms Paraiyas and Panchamas. The term Paraiya meant something mean and despicable, while the term Panchama denoted one who is an out caste. During his debate Rajah loudly shouted! - We are the original inhabitants of this land and we never submitted to the yoke of Chaturvarna (Castes). We are the true descendants of the original inhabitants and preservers of the original Adi-Dravidian civilization

This resolution (No.225) was supported by Rao Bahadur T.Emperumal Chetti, M.C.Mad.urai Pillai, K.Srinivasa Iyengar and S.Somasundaram Pillai. They pleaded for the removal of the stigma and extended support to the resolution. The resolution was carried out and the Government issued an order in 1922 directing the use of the term Adi-Dravidas in Tamil Districts, Adi-Andhra in Telugu Districts and Adi-Karnataka in Karnatakas districts in place of the names like Panchamas, Paraiyas, Madigas and Malas etc. An order was issued on 25.3.1922 to record in the Government documents. But, this order was not fully enforced until 1924. A volley of questions by R.Veeraiyan were raised against the officials who did not comply with the order of the Government. Chief Minister stated that the Government would not use the caste names of the Depressed Classes and that it would take any action if any one used the caste names instead of the term Adi-Dravidas.

Most of the people from Depressed Classes were not even aware of the change in the name of their Community. A few Communities started calling themselves as Adi-Dravidas, hut many other did not. Anyhow, the term Adi-Dravidas was known even before 1922. It was found in the Census Report of 1911 and some castes of the Depressed Classes were entered as Adi-Dravidas. And in the Census Report of 1921 there were 50,015 Adi-Dravidas in Vellore District in 1931 and 1951 Census there were 16,19,277 and 19,53,669 Adi-Dravidas respectively. The population of Paraiyas and Pallas were also enumerated separately. This was because, the Government Officials did not take keen interest in enumerating these castes to the column of Adi-Dravidaa. Secondly. the Depressed Classes themselves were not aware of the change of their name into Adi-Dravidas. Thirdly, from the very beginning the Pallas did not want to change their caste names from Pallas to

Adi-Dravidas and they preferred the name Devendra Kula Vellalars instead of Adi-Dravidas. Following the examples of the Untouchables in Vellore District, the Untouchables of Andhra and Karnataka began to call themselves as Adi-Andhra and Adi-Kamat.aka respectively. It should be noted that the change of name did not either socially or materially, benefit to the Depressed Classes. The Superintendent of Census Report M.W.M.Yeatts said, There is something infinitely pathetic in the vain idea that a change of name can reverse the stiima lasting for centuries

Paraiyas

The Paraiyas form a sizable portion of the Tamil Society. It is from their caste name it can be considered that the word Paraiya meaning outcastes has been coined and added to the rich repository of English language. The term Paraiya is derived from the root word Parai which means a kind of drum and Paraiyas are considered to be traditional drum beaters. One who beats Parai or drum is called Paraiya, Paraiyas are not the only drum beaters but others also beating kind of drums, In Kannada also word Parai means drum but the drum beaters of Kannada Desa are not called as Paraiyas but as Holeyas. The Barbers of Vellore District are beating drums at the festive seasons but they are not called as Paraiyas. Lord Siva is also beating a drum called Udukkai and his devotee Nandhi is also beating a kind of drum called Mathalam. and they are not called as Paraiyaa. It is only one section of the Paraiyas that act as a drummers. Nor is the occupation confined to Paraiyas. It seems in the highest degree improbable that a large and at one time powerful community should bear its name to an occasional occupation. The beaters of battle drum are called Yallunas and Pullaiyas in ancient Tamil Literature. The Pulaiyas arc also described as drum beaters in funeral processions. Thus, the word Paraiyas as a professional name must have been applied at first only to those Pulaiyas who were beating drums in funeral processions. Later on, the word somehow came to be applied to all other Pulaiyas also.

The word Paraiyan is found once, in Sangam Classic . Purananuru and it is not found in Tioakara Nihantu a Tamil Dictionary of the 11th century A.D. But the term Paraiyas is found in many places in the inscriptions of the Cholas of the 11th

and 12th centuries A.D. Therefore. Paraiya was not a popular term during the Sangam Age. Those who acted as royal herald to announce the royal message to the public by beating drum were called as Valluvas and not as Paraiyas. Those who beat drum during funeral occasions were called Puloiyas but not as Paraiyas..

Panchamas

The paraiyas are also called as Panchamas. The Aryan society was of four Varnas or Chaturvarnas such as Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vysyas, and Shudras. The whole society had been covered within these four classes. The Untouchables were left out of these fourfold divisions. Therefore, they were called as Avarnas or not within the fold of Varna group. They are also called as outcastes or not having the caste. But in the later days they were called as the fifth Varna or Panchama. Generally, it means the poor people. During the British period, these people were allotted with Purarnbok lands called Panchami lands and were called as Panchamas and Paraiyas.

Valluvas

Valluvas are a section of the paraiyas, who enjoyed the status of the priest hood in ancient Tamil Society. It is attested by literary and inscriptional evidences. Stuart. in his Census Report of 1891 mentions that the Valluvas were priests of the Pallava kings before the coming of the Brahmin Priests. They are even now acting as the priests of Scheduled Castes who do not employ the Brahmins as priests in their ceremonies. The Valluvas are also noted for their erudition in Tamil literature and skill in foretelling the future. They are also expert as rural doctors. Tiruvalluvar the author of Tirukkural is considered as a Valluva by caste. Tivakara Nikantu a Tamil Dictionary of 11th century AD describes the Valluvas as Royal Priests who performed the funeral rites in the Kings house hold.

As the Valluvas considered themselves a section of the Paraiyas they were also called as Valluva-Paraiyas. After 1935, when the Adi-Dravida Mahaiana Sabha was deviated from the spirit of communalism and splited, most of the leaders joined in the Indian National Congress. Raiaii, when he formed his ministry in 1937, one V.I. Munuswamy Pillai of Adi-Dravida - section was included in his cabinet.

Therefore, the Valluvas who have been integrated in the Adi-Dravida Mahajana Sabha ceased away and formed their own Sangham called The Madras Presidency Valluvar - Mahajana Sangam and Astrology College and this was registered under the Societies Registration Act, 1860. The Sangam changed its name as The South India Valluvar Marutjana Sangam¹¹ The head quarters of Valluvar Mahajana Sangham was established at No.10, Ammaiappa-Mudali Street, Old Washermenpet, Madras and K.Vuavalinga Nayanar was elected as its Secretary and K.S.Chokkalinganayanar 88 Vice Chairman. This Association conducted so many conferences and wanted to remain in the list of Scheduled Castes only. They wanted to be called 88 ..Valluvas and their caste title to be recognised as Nayanar one of the titles of the Tiruvalluvar.

Chakkilians

Another section of the Paraiyas are called Chakkilians but they are not the natives of Tamil country. They seem to be the immigrants from Andhra Desa and Mysore State and their mother tongue is Telugu or Kanada. But the Chakkilians of Vellore District called themselves as Arunthathiyars and they speak Tamil only. Most of them are engaged in tannings. The Chakkilians, like Paraiyas are an ancient people of the Dravida Country and they are also branded as Untouchables. They called themselves as Arunthathiyar connected with the name of the Purana Purushar, Vasisitas wife. They formed their own association called Arunthathiyar Mahajana Shabha and its head quarters was at Mettupalayam, Vyasarpadi, Perambur, Madras. L.C.Gurusamy (1885-1966), the leader of the Arunthathiyar Mahajana Sabha started separate Night Schools for this community. In 1920 he was nominated as a member of the Madras Legislative Council as the representative of the Arunthathiyar Community. And he was nominated for three times and hence he enjoyed the Council membership for nearly 10 years.

Pallas

The Pallas are a section of Paraiyas mostly found in the southern region of Vellore District. It is to be noted that the Pallas are not found in the Vellore District. Since they were segregated from the village and forced to live in low lying

region (or) Pallam in Tamil), it seems they were called as Pallas (one who lives in Pa1.lam or Pit). They claim their superiority over Paraiyas and Chakkiliyars because Pallas are not the beef eaters (or) engaged in tanning or digging grave yard and the like menial works. Nowadays they called themselves as Devendra Kula Vellalas. The Pallas (or) Devendrakula Vellalas in the first instance called their association as Devendrakula Velala-Adi-Draavidar Sangham. Later, they called themselves as Devendrakulathar or descendants of Indra, Lord of Devas. Kudumpan, Mannadi. Mooppan etc, are the titles assumed by them.

Conclusion

This study the evolution of history, certain terminologies were also subject to change and caste names of Untouchables also have met. their evolutionary changes. The term Adi-Sudra was once used to denote the Untouchables under the Chaturvarna system as the Untouchables were a exploited class. The term Panchamas denoted not only the fifth vama but also poor and landless people. The term Paraiya meant as drum-beater. The term Pulia denoted one who deals with flush, skin and hides. All these terms were denoted the Untouchables of Tamil regions in ancient times simply meaning the low or degraded people. The British administrators termed these people as Depressed Classes. They coined this term because of their depressed social and economic status. Therefore. Dr.B.R.Ambedkar and Rettaimalai Srinivasan used this term in the proceedings of the Round Table Conferences and in their memoranda submitted to the British Government. When the Constitution of 1935 was introduced, the term Scheduled Caste was incorporated in it to denote certain classes of people who were eligible for the protection by the Government.

Thus the people of Vellore region played a conspicuous and vital role in the freedom struggle. They took part actively irrespective of the caste and creed or faith in the Khilafat movement, Non-Co-operation movement, Civil Disobedience movement, Quit India movement etc., Many of their prominent leaders were subjected to harassment, torture, humiliation and death by the British officials. They sacrificed their lives and property for the emancipation of India from the British

domination, Viewing the scenario in retrospect, Vellore district can boast of an unbroken history of over the years with its limitless variety.

The Adi-Dravida Mahajana Sabha in its conference held at Madras on 8th January 1928 passed a resolution and sent to the Government and other public bodies to use the term Adi-Hindu instead of Depressed Classes. But it was opposed by the members of the North Arcot District Adi-Dravida Mahajanasabba. They said, that the Adi-Dravidas are not Hindus, and therefore the term Adi-Hindus should not be used in the place of Adi-Dravida, In 1921 Census the Paraiyas, Panchamas, Pallas, Vettiyanas etc. were listed as Adi-Dravidas, and as a consequence the figures for Adi-Dravidas showed a marked increase. Among the Depressed classes also there were sections spreading into Tamil, Telugu and Kannada languages. There were Malas and Madigas of Telugu speaking Depressed classes and Holiyas of Kannada speaking Depressed classes. The Vellore district may be called the mirror of Tamil Nadu history in which the natural boundaries flora and fauna are the bedrock of the history of the country.

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